

Impact of Metformin on the Warburg Effect on Cancer Cells

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ABSTRACT

It is complex to understand all the mechanisms by which tumor cells use for their survival. The aim of the present review is to propose the mechanisms by which metformin would be beneficial in the context of cancer through the inhibition of the Warburg effect. A literature review of the Warburg effect and the mechanism of action of metformin was carried out to determine a theoretical relationship between metformin consumption and inhibition of tumor cell metabolism. There are several mechanisms through which metformin could antagonize tumor cells. As authors, we consider it of vital importance to know these effects in order to extrapolate them to experimental studies and seek the maximum benefit for patients, using the resources we have to date.

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INTRODUCTION

It is complex to understand all the mechanisms by which tumor cells use for their survival. Initially, there is uncontrolled proliferation and the acquisition of genetic alterations that allow them to grow outside the primary site, giving them adaptive advantages over healthy cells¹.

During the 1920s, Otto Warburg and his colleagues observed that tumors utilized large amounts of glucose relative to the surrounding tissue, noting that the rate of fermentative glycolysis increased even under aerobic conditions. It is known that fermentation is independent of oxygen, so Warburg's phenomenon was a contradiction to the Pasteur effect^{1, 2}.

Metformin is an oral antidiabetic belonging to the biguanides, it decreases hyperglycemia through hepatic suppression of glucose production. In addition, it increases insulin sensitivity, enhances peripheral glucose uptake (by inducing

phosphorylation of GLUT4-enhancing factor), decreases insulin-induced suppression of fatty acid oxidation, and decreases glucose absorption from the gastrointestinal tract³. However, the underlying molecular mechanism is only partially understood. Inhibition of the mitochondrial respiratory chain, activation of AMP-activated protein kinase, inhibition of glucagon-induced elevation of cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP), consequent activation of protein kinase A (PKA), inhibition of mitochondrial glycerophosphate dehydrogenase, and an effect on the gut microbiota have been proposed as potential mechanisms⁴⁻⁶.

The aim of the present review is to propose the mechanisms by which metformin would be beneficial in the context of cancer through the inhibition of the Warburg effect.

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METHODS

A literature review on the Warburg effect and the mechanism of action of metformin was carried out to determine a theoretical relationship between metformin consumption and the inhibition of tumor cell metabolism; for this purpose, a search was carried out in several databases, preferably using those published 5 years ago, although some older ones were included since their relevance is justified.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Metabolism of healthy cells

Under normal circumstances the cell produces ATP to meet its needs by coupling two catabolic mechanisms; firstly, glycolysis, which consists of 10 enzymatic reactions responsible for degrading glucose to pyruvate, and secondly, the Krebs cycle, which provides greater energy efficiency during the complete oxidation of glucose due to the presence of oxygen. Pyruvate is condensed within the mitochondria by coenzyme A and oxaloacetate. Complete oxidation of pyruvate continues through the tricarboxylic acid cycle, the respiratory chain and oxidative phosphorylation. Due to both mechanisms approximately 90% of the energy required for normal cell function is obtained^{1, 7}.

Metabolism in the context of cancer

At the cellular level tumors present evolutionary advantages for lactate secretion⁸. The expression and coupling of vascular endothelial growth factor and its receptor respond to different stimuli for angiogenesis, among these stimuli is the increased expression of hypoxia inducible factor 1, which in turn is positively stimulated by the acidic and anaerobic environment. Other stimuli involved include activation of oncogenes such as RAS, MYC, AKT and mutation of tumor suppressor genes such as p53. Stimulation of VEGF and its receptor are intended to generate greater oxygenation to the cells to promote oxidative metabolism and suppress fermentative glycolysis, however, paradoxically, metastasis is promoted⁹.

Under oxygen limitation pyruvate is reduced to lactate. If there are failures in the respiratory chain the oxidation of NADH+H⁺ does not occur by this pathway. Because of this, the transition from pyruvate to lactate is a critical point in the metabolism of tumor cells¹⁰. In tumor cells, changes in the expression of lactate dehydrogenase enzyme isoforms have been demonstrated and it was observed that tumor cells deficient in lactate dehydrogenase showed increased mitochondrial respiration¹¹. The acidic environment is hostile and normal cells die due to lack of cellular mechanisms to adapt to the extracellular acidity^{12, 13}. This promotes the adaptation of the fittest cells that resist an acidic environment in the context of rapid proliferation, in turn preventing the mounting of an immune response against it and thus facilitating selection

mechanisms for uncontrolled growth of tumor tissue¹⁴.

Direct and indirect antitumor mechanisms of metformin

The mechanism of action of metformin involves negative regulation of the insulin/insulin-like growth factor axis, a mechanism that has been demonstrated in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and women with polycystic ovary syndrome¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Current observations have focused on the ability of this drug to activate AMPK through the tumor suppressor LKB1, a tumor suppressor kinase whose inactivation leads to Peutz-Jeghers syndrome^{18, 19}. Activation of AMPK, results in a positive regulation of oxidative metabolism and reduced anabolism²⁰. In addition to direct phosphorylation effects on key metabolic targets such as acetyl CoA and phosphofructokinase 2, AMPK activation also leads to mTOR inhibition that decreases signaling through Akt kinase and decreases the efficiency of protein synthesis through decreased phosphorylation of mTOR targets 4EBP-1 and S6K²¹⁻²⁴. Cap-dependent inhibition of translation in response to metformin can decrease the expression of Her2, an oncogene and cyclin D1²⁵⁻²⁷.

Finally, AMPK-independent antitumor effects of metformin action have been demonstrated, such as inhibition of Rag GTPase-dependent mTOR and growth inhibition of AMPK-silenced ovarian cancer cells²⁸. Researchers described that metformin could inhibit mitochondrial oxidation of complex I-dependent substrates in hepatocytes, and this effect extrapolates to isolated mitochondria²⁹. This inhibition of complex I may contribute to AMPK activation due to decreased oxidative phosphorylation capacity and a consequent decrease in the ATP/AMP ratio, a phenomenon that explains the lactic acidosis observed in response to high doses of metformin³⁰.

DISCUSSION

It has been consistently shown that inhibition of hepatic gluconeogenesis is an AMPK-independent consequence of decreased intracellular ATP levels, a fact that suggests that the pleiotropic effects of this agent could be the result of a targeted effect on the mitochondrial electron transport chain³¹. This effect is more intriguing in light of recent observations demonstrating that inhibition of electron transport in cancer cells is fatal to cancer cells³²⁻³⁴, because the accumulation of NADH in the mitochondrial matrix inhibits the Krebs cycle and its associated anaplerotic reactions that sustain biomass generation³⁵. Furthermore, it is suggested that electron transport, uncoupled from oxidative phosphorylation, antagonizes the initiation of apoptosis in tumor cells^{35, 36}, supporting the hypothesis that the chemotherapeutic effects of

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metformin may result from its ability to inhibit the mitochondrial complex.

The authors of this literature review considered this topic in order to establish a causal relationship between these effects of metformin and the mechanisms of cancer. It is thanks to the arguments reflected in the preceding paragraphs that we justify the need for this paper.

Now, with regard to the bibliography we have selected for this work, we were able to reach the conclusion that it is refined, since the articles and books that compose it have followed international parameters to be valid, a reflection of this is that they appear in scientific journals or belong to prestigious publishers, as the case may be. In addition, they are conclusive in their results.

In the strict sense of the word, we are aware that this cannot be a discussion, since the central thesis of the present work has not been to confront information, but rather to try to enunciate the molecular mechanisms by which metformin would be beneficial in selected types of cancer.

CONCLUSION

As authors, we consider it vitally important to know these effects in order to extrapolate them to experimental studies and seek the maximum benefit for patients, using the resources we have to date.

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